

FRICION AND WEAR BEHAVIOR OF METAL MATRIX-

GRAPHITE FIBER COMPOSITES*

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The wear and friction properties of metal matrix-graphite fiber composites produced through the process of liquid-metal infiltration were determined in the unlubricated condition at room temperature. Stationary slider specimens were pressed against rotating steel rings at loads between 3 and 30 N and at a sliding speed of 0.684 m/sec. The materials examined include a variety of matrix materials (several aluminum alloys, copper, and tin) infiltrated into a variety of continuous graphite fibers (rayon and polyacrylonitrile precursor fibers). The results indicate that the type of fiber significantly influences the tribological behavior of the aluminum alloy matrix composites. No significant effect of fiber orientation with respect to the wear and friction properties was observed. Except for the aluminum alloy-rayon precursor fiber composite, the wear rates and friction of the metal matrix-graphite fiber composites are superior to those of the unreinforced matrix material.

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Introduction

High-modulus, high-strength graphite or carbon fibers have stimulated considerable interest as a component for advanced bearing and seal materials. These fibers offer the advantage of providing high strength and stiffness and low density reinforcements for conventional bearing materials, as well as a potential source of in situ dry lubrication. These qualities are required for high-speed, high-load, and high-temperature bearing and seal applications.

Most of the work to develop such bearing materials has been with polymeric matrices.¹⁻⁶ Both thermosetting resins - such as polyimide, epoxide, polyester, and polyphenylene - and thermoplastic polymers - such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), polyethylene, polyacetal, and nylon 66 - have been reinforced with graphite fibers for wear and friction evaluation. The fibers used most often in these studies have been both the low-modulus and high-modulus polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor graphite fibers in either the continuous or chopped form and either unidirectionally aligned or randomly oriented. The type of fiber used in reinforced polymers has a significant effect on the tribological properties. Giltrow and Lancaster³ reported that the wear behavior of high-modulus (pyrolysed at 2873 K) fiber composites is independent of the mating surface material, while that of high-strength (pyrolysed at 1773 K) fiber composites was very sensitive to the mating material. On the other hand, the wear behavior of the high-modulus fiber composites is dependent on mating surface roughness, while that of the high-strength fiber composites is not. Scott et al.⁷ found that PTFE-graphite composite ball bearing cages were more wear resistant than the high-strength graphite fiber was used rather than the high-modulus fiber. The shape of the fiber may also be significant as shown by the work of Berg et al.⁶ in which the tribological properties differed between a circular cross section fiber composite and a "dog-bone" cross section fiber composite. Other factors that affect the wear behavior of polymer-graphite composites are temperature of sliding⁵ and fiber orientation.²

Wear and friction behavior of metal matrix-graphite fiber composites has been investigated to a lesser extent. These materials offer the greatest potential for high-load and elevated temperature applications, however, their state of technological development lags behind that of the polymer matrix composites. Giltrow and Lancaster⁸ studied the wear and friction behavior of composites consisting of up to 25 vol% randomly oriented, chopped carbon fibers in lead, silver, copper, nickel, and cobalt. The wear rates of these materials against tool steel were significantly improved over those of the parent metals, but the friction was not reduced. Although the wear behavior of these composites was promising, they did suffer from two serious drawbacks. First, no improvement in high-temperature wear properties was produced, and second, the mechanical

properties of the composites were degraded compared to the parent metals. These deficiencies are probably the result of fiber damage induced by the hot-pressing technique that was used to fabricate the composites. More recently, Old et al.⁹ infiltrated continuous filaments of graphite fiber with liquid lead-tin alloys, producing composites with 65 to 70 vol% fiber. The tribological properties were comparable to those of commercial bearing materials, but the mechanical properties were only 25 to 30% of that predicted by the rule of mixtures. Better mechanical properties were obtained with a low volume fraction (10-15%) of chopped fibers, but there was some sacrifice in tribological properties.

In this work, a number of metal matrix-continuous filament graphite fiber composites have been prepared by liquid-metal infiltration. These composites contained 30 vol% fiber and had strengths within 80% of that predicted by the rule of mixtures¹⁰ as well as excellent fatigue properties.¹¹

Materials

Composites were produced by liquid-metal infiltration of a number of graphite yarns, which included those from rayon and PAN precursor materials. Table I summarizes the properties of these fibers. Compared with the PAN-based fibers, the rayon-based fibers are characterized by a higher modulus and a lower strength, and possess a crenulated cross section versus a round cross section. In addition to the mechanical and physical differences, there are also chemical and crystallographic differences between these two types of fiber arising from differences in thermal treatment. The rayon-based fiber is more completely graphitized and possesses a greater degree of crystallographic orientation.

The matrix materials used in this study are listed in Table II, along with the nominal alloy compositions and their typical strengths and moduli. The composites examined in this study are listed in Table III.

The composites were produced by applying a thin deposit of titanium and boron through chemical vapor deposition prior to immersion into the liquid metal. By this process, composite wire is produced that has a diameter that depends upon the number of fibers in the graphite yarn. For instance, 8-strand Thornel 50 yarn, which consists of 11,520 filaments, has a final wire diameter of ~1.5 mm. The wire was consolidated into 6-mm-square bars by hot-pressing at temperatures above the solidus in the two-phase solid-liquid state for the alloy matrix composites and by pressing near the melting point for the unalloyed metal matrix composites. The mating

material was AISI 4620 steel (nominal composition, in weight percent: 0.2 C, 0.5 Mn, 0.25 Si, 1.75 Ni, 0.25 Mo), which was heat-treated to Rockwell hardness 58 to 63 Rc.

Typical microstructures for cross sections that are normal to the fiber direction for these composites are shown in Fig. 1. Figure 1(a) is the microstructure of the copper-Thornel 50 composite, which is also typical of all aluminum alloy-rayon based composites. Figure 1(b) is the microstructure of the tin-Thornel 50 composite. The major difference between these two microstructures is the density of fibers within a given bundle. The tin matrix tends to draw the fibers closer together during infiltration. Figure 1(c) is the microstructure of Al 201-Thornel 300 and is typical of the fiber distribution for all aluminum alloy-PAN fiber composites.

Experimental Procedures

The wear test specimen geometry consists of a stationary slider specimen 4.75 mm square and a rotating cylindrical mating surface as indicated in Fig. 2. The mating surface is a standard alpha wear tester ring specimen. As the wear scar takes the radius of the ring specimen during wearing, the wear volume of the slider specimen can be calculated from simple geometric considerations of the volume of a segment of a cylinder of radius r .

The slider specimen is held in a self-aligning fixture to produce a uniform wear scar length c , along the wear track width t . The normal loads are applied by means of weights, and the friction force is transmitted by a sensing beam to a 890-N load cell whose signal is amplified and recorded on a light beam oscillograph. The sensing beam is designed to contain the horizontal motion of the specimen while yielding to vertical movements of the specimen as it wears; thus, the normal force between the specimen and the counter face is independent of the amount of wear.

The mating surface is rotated at an angular velocity of 39.2 rad/sec, which results in a linear velocity of 0.684 m/sec. The slider specimens are milled to a typical surface finish of 0.3 μm rms, and the mating ring specimens have a ground surface finish (0.13 to 0.39 μm rms) as obtained from the Faville-LeValley Corporation. The slider and mating surface specimens are cleaned with degreasing agents prior to testing. All tests are run dry without lubricant.

After each test, the length of the wear scar is measured by an optical comparator in order to calculate the wear volume. Wear debris obscuring the edges of the wear scan can limit the measurement accuracy to ± 0.3 mm, which produces a wear volume uncertainty of 0.4%. The surfaces of both the slider specimen and the mating specimen are examined with the scanning electron microscope (SEM) after each test.

Results and Discussion

The wear and friction behavior of the various metal matrix-graphite fiber composites examined in the unlubricated condition in this study are summarized in Table III. Experiments indicated that the initial wear rates for aluminum alloy matrix composites with either PAN or rayon precursor fibers are very high and decrease rapidly with sliding time. The friction and wear behavior of one composite, Al 201-Thornel 300, was examined up to 200 min of sliding under a normal load of 10 N. The results are plotted in Fig. 3. The initial high wear rate decreases rapidly during the first 10 min of sliding and reaches a minimum between 20 and 40 min followed by a slight increase. The scatter in the wear rate data appears to be greatest at the initial sliding time (≤ 2 min) and at the 200-min interval. The friction also appears to be increasing gradually over this time period with the greatest rate of increase occurring during the initial period of sliding. This behavior indicates an initial wear-in period possibly associated with the filling of the grooves in the mating ring specimen.

The change in surface appearance of an Al 201-Thornel 300 slider specimen and a mating AISI 4620 steel ring after 2 min of sliding under a 6-N load is shown in the SEM micrographs of Fig. 4. The appearance of the machined composite surface [Fig. 4(a)] indicates a considerable degree of metal smearing with imbedded graphite debris. After 2 min of sliding, the surface layer is worn sufficiently to reveal the ends of the fibers [Fig. 4(c)]. Smearing of metal over the edges of the fibers is evident. The grinding grooves on the steel mating ring specimen are not significantly worn after 2 min of sliding, but wear debris has collected on its surface [compare Figs. 4(b) and 4(d)].

The appearance of both the slider specimen and the ring specimen after 200 min does not provide any clues as to the cause of the slight increase in wear rates after 80 min of sliding. The slider appearance does not seem to be significantly different than after 2 min, and the ring specimen has a smooth burnished appearance after 200 min.

The effect of normal load on the wear rate of an Al 201-Thornel 300 composite is shown in Fig. 5. Although the scatter in the data is large, the trend of increasing wear rate with load is unmistakable. Near a 30-N load, the wear rate increases drastically to almost 170×10^{-14} m³/sec. The coefficient of friction, conversely, remains somewhat stable with loads up to 30 N (see Table III).

The tribological behavior of the various aluminum matrix-graphite fiber composites is shown in Fig. 6. Eight aluminum matrix composites have been investigated that represent three alloys and five fibers. The specimens were tested under a 6-N load and were run for 10 min. It is immediately obvious that the wear rates for

the PAN-based graphite fiber composites, such as Hercules A, Fortafil 4R, and Thornel 300, are significantly less than for the rayon-based graphite fibers, Thornel 50 and Thornel 75. For the cases of Al 6061 and Al 201 matrices, the difference between the two types of fibers is an order of magnitude. The Al A413 alloy resulted in a somewhat less dramatic difference between the fibers. In contrast to the wear behavior, the friction properties of the rayon-based fiber composites are half those of the PAN-based fiber composites, regardless of matrix alloy. The Al A413-Thornel 75 composite has the optimum combination of wear resistance and friction properties.

A surface examination by means of scanning electron microscopy of the Al 201-Thornel 50 (rayon-based) composites after 2 min of sliding at a 6-N normal load revealed no gross differences in appearance between the slider specimens [compare Figs. 7(a) and 7(b)]. Both composites show metal smearing and the imbedding of fragments into their surfaces. The surfaces of the exposed fibers for the rayon-based composites exhibit a greater degree of surface contour than those of the PAN-based composites. This difference as well as the difference in tribological properties may be related to the difference in the degree of graphitization and crystal orientation between the two.

A significant difference in appearance of the mating ring specimens used with the different composites is evident in Figs. 7(c) and 7(d). The PAN-based fiber composite resulted in only a relatively small amount of material transfer to the ring [Fig. 7(c)], while extensive material transfer to the ring can be seen for the rayon-based fiber composite [Fig. 7(d)].

All of the aluminum alloy matrix-PAN based fiber composites investigated in this study are considered low-modulus fibers. If these materials are analogous to the plastic matrix composites, a significant difference in wear behavior is expected between these low-modulus PAN-based fiber composites and the high-modulus ones.

The tests described thus far have been for specimens oriented with the fibers normal to the sliding surface (A orientation). A few tests were also performed with the fibers parallel to the sliding surface with the sliding direction either normal (B orientation) or parallel (C orientation) to the sliding direction. The results of these tests are illustrated in Fig. 8 and represent both PAN-based and rayon-based fiber composites. The wear rates for all three composites appear to be unaffected by fiber orientation. These results are in contrast to the behavior found by Lancaster² on polyester resin matrix-graphite composites in which significantly higher wear rates were found for the C orientation and the lowest wear rates were found for the A orientation.

The effect of orientation on the friction behavior of the metal matrix composite is somewhat inconsistent, as seen in Fig. 8. For the Al 201-Thornel 50 composite, the lowest friction occurred for the A orientation and the highest for the C orientation, which was almost twice that of A. The B orientation resulted in a friction value intermediate between the A and C orientations. Conversely, the coefficient of friction was independent of orientation for the Al 6061-Fortafil 4R composite. For the Al A413-Fortafil 4R composite, the coefficient of friction is again greatest for the C orientation, but the B orientation has the lowest friction. Thus, for the three composites examined, each exhibited a distinct friction behavior with respect to the fiber orientation.

It is interesting to compare the wear and friction behavior of various metal matrix-graphite composites with that of the matrix material alone. Figure 9 shows that both tin-Thornel 50 and copper-Thornel 50 composites result in improved wear resistance compared to their matrix materials. The improvement in the friction properties for these composites is even more pronounced than that of the wear properties. For the Al 6061, only the PAN-based fiber composite results in an increased wear resistance compared to the matrix material. The rayon-based fiber composite actually has a poorer wear resistance than did the alloy although an improvement in the friction properties was achieved for the composite. It should be noted that the improvement in wear properties for the tin and copper composites is achieved in spite of the fact that rayon-based fibers are used.

Figure 10 compares the SEM micrographs of the surfaces of tin-Thornel 50, copper-Thornel 50, and Al 6061-Fortafil 4R after 10 min of sliding under a 6-N load. The surface appearances of the three composite materials are significantly different. Figure 10(a) (upper) shows the worn surface of the tin-matrix composite material to consist primarily of exposed fiber ends with streaks of smeared metal. The close packing of the fibers for this composite is a characteristic originating from the infiltration process. Graphite debris in the area of smeared metal is evident at higher magnifications, as seen in Fig. 10(a) (lower). The wear surface of the copper-matrix composite consists primarily of smeared matrix material, as seen in Fig. 10(b) (upper and lower). For the aluminum alloy matrix composite, Fig. 10(c) (upper), metal smearing is considerably less than in the other composites. The Al 6061 matrix is worn down beneath the level of the fiber, leaving it in relief over large areas of the worn surface, as in Fig. 10(c) (lower). The Al 201 matrix with either Thornel 50 (rayon-based fiber) or Thornel 300 (PAN-based fiber) has a greater degree of surface metal smearing than does the Al 6061-Fortafil 4R composite, but the smearing is less than that of the copper-matrix composite [compare Figs. 7(a), 7(b), 10(a) (upper), and 10(c) (upper)]. The degree of metal smearing does not seem to be related to the wear rate or the friction of the various composites.

Conclusions

● The wear rates and the friction of aluminum alloy matrix-graphite fiber composites are influenced significantly by the type of fiber used. Composites containing rayon precursor fibers result in half the friction but with wear rates that are as much as an order of magnitude greater than those containing PAN precursor fibers. The alloy composition of the matrix has a less pronounced influence on the tribological properties of these composites.

● The orientation of the fibers with respect to the sliding direction does not influence the wear rates of the aluminum alloy matrix composites, but the effect on friction is not consistent among the various composites.

● Except for the aluminum alloy-rayon precursor fiber composite, the wear rates and friction of the metal matrix-graphite fiber composites are superior to those of the unreinforced matrix material.

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Table I. Graphite Fiber Materials

Fiber		Fiber Diam, m	Tensile Strength, MPa	Young's Modulus, GPa	Cross Section Shape	Fibers per Strand	Strands per Tow
Type	Precursor						
Thornel 50	Rayon	6	2170 ± 630	438 ± 69	Crenulated	1440	8
Thornel 75	Rayon	5	2468 ± 696	578 ± 138	Crenulated	1440	8
Thornel 300	PAN	7	3117 ± 820	220 ± 35	Circular	3000	4
Fortafil 4R	PAN	8	2406 ± 641	218 ± 30	Circular	6000	1
Hercules A	PAN	8	3496 ± 765	243 ± 29	Circular	10000	1

Table II. Matrix Materials

Material ^a	Tensile Strength, MPa	Young's Modulus, GPa
Aluminum Alloy 201 (4.7 Cu, 0.7 Ag, 0.3 Mg, 0.3 Mn, 0.3 Ti)	186	69
Aluminum Alloy 6061 (1 Mg, 0.6 Si, 0.25 Cr, 0.3 Cu)	124	69
Aluminum Alloy A413 (12 Si, 0.6 Cu, 0.1 Mg, 1.3 Fe)	269	69
Copper	221	117
Tin	14	49

^aCompositions given in weight percent

Table III. Summary of Results of Wear and Friction Behavior of Various Metal Matrix-Graphite Fiber Composites

Composite		Orientation ^a	Normal Load, N	Sliding Time, min	Average Wear Rate, 10^{-14} m ³ /sec	Average Coefficient of Friction	Number of Specimens Tested		
Matrix	Fiber								
Al 201 - Thornel 50		A	6	2	104.2	0.29	5		
		A	6	10	43.1	0.28	2		
		B	6	2	119.0	0.37	3		
		C	6	2	107.0	0.54	2		
Al 201 - Thornel 300		A	10	1	25.6	0.42	2		
		A	10	2	17.7	0.48	3		
		A	10	5	9.5	0.65	2		
		A	10	6	8.3	0.64	1		
		A	10	10	6.4	0.64	3		
		A	10	20	4.7	0.69	3		
		A	10	40	4.4	0.77	2		
		A	10	60	4.6	0.75	2		
		A	10	80	5.0	0.74	2		
		A	10	100	5.8	0.80	3		
		A	10	200	8.4	0.83	3		
		A	3	10	2.0	0.51	2		
		A	5	10	4.0	0.73	1		
		A	6	10	7.1	0.46	1		
		A	8	10	4.3	0.62	2		
		A	10	10	6.2	0.68	1		
		A	12	10	13.8	0.60	2		
		A	16	10	17.5	0.67	3		
		A	20	10	6.8	0.57	1		
		A	22	10	18.8	0.64	1		
		A	24	10	22.2	0.65	1		
		A	26	10	31.7	0.62	1		
		A	30	10	168.9	0.48	1		
		Al 6061-Thornel 50		A	6	2	83.0	0.28	2
				A	6	5	64.2	0.31	1
				A	6	10	36.2	0.25	2
Al 6061-Thornel 75		A	6	2	61.8	0.26	1		
		A	6	10	32.9	0.25	2		
Al 6061-Hercules A		A	6	10	3.1	0.52	2		
		A	16	20	13.5	0.56	1		

^aOrientation

A Fibers normal to sliding surface

B Fibers parallel to sliding surface and fiber axis normal to sliding direction

C Fibers parallel to sliding surface and fiber axis parallel to sliding direction

Table III. Summary of Results of Wear and Friction Behavior of Various Metal Matrix-Graphite Fiber Composites (Continued)

Composite		Orientation ^a	Normal Load, N	Sliding Time, min	Average Wear Rate, 10^{-14} m ³ /sec	Average Coefficient of Friction	Number of Specimens Tested
Matrix	Fiber						
Al 6061-Fortafil 4R		A	6	20	2.5	0.55	1
		A	16	20	7.5	0.53	1
		B	16	20	6.2	0.52	1
		C	16	20	6.7	0.51	1
Al A413-Thornel 75		A	6	2	34.2	0.45	1
		A	6	10	7.7	0.27	2
		A	6	20	4.4	0.26	1
Al A413-Fortafil 4R		A	6	10	2.4	0.57	2
		A	16	20	7.4	0.49	1
		B	16	20	7.8	0.40	1
		C	16	20	9.2	0.65	1
Al 6061	---	-	6	10	29.9	0.61	2
Copper	-Thornel 50	A	6	10	7.3	0.17	2
Copper	---	-	6	10	18.3	1.00	2
Tin	-Thornel 50	A	6	10	16.5	0.18	2
Tin	---	-	6	10	27.4	0.92	2

^aOrientation

A Fibers normal to sliding surface

B Fibers parallel to sliding surface and fiber axis normal to sliding direction

C Fibers parallel to sliding surface and fiber axis parallel to sliding direction

(a) COPPER-THORNEL 50

(b) TIN-THORNEL 50

(c) Al 201-THORNEL 300

1. Metallographic cross section of typical composites used in friction and wear studies.

2. Specimen configuration used in friction and wear testing apparatus.

3. Effect of sliding time on wear and friction behavior of Al 201-Thornel 300 composite loaded to 10 N.

(a) AS-MACHINED SURFACE
OF COMPOSITE SPECIMEN

(b) AS-GROUND SURFACE
OF MATING RING SPECIMEN

(c) WORN SURFACE OF
COMPOSITE SPECIMEN

(d) WORN SURFACE OF
MATING RING SPECIMEN

4. SEM micrographs of as-machined and worn (2 min of sliding at 6 N load at 0.684 m/sec) surfaces of Al 201-Thornel 300 and mating 4620 steel ring specimens.

5. Effect of normal load on wear rate of Al 201-Thornel 300 composite.

6. Friction and wear behavior of aluminum alloy-graphite fiber composites. (Shaded bars indicated PAN-based precursor fibers.)

(a) Al 201-THORNEL 300 SLIDER SPECIMEN

(b) Al 201-THORNEL 50 SLIDER SPECIMEN

(c) MATING RING SPECIMEN FOR Al 201-THORNEL 300

(d) MATING RING SPECIMEN FOR Al 201-THORNEL 50

7. Comparison of SEM surface appearance of slider and ring specimens for aluminum matrix composites with rayon- and PAN-based fibers.

8. Wear and friction behavior of three composites for three distinct directions of fiber orientation. (Note the order-of-magnitude difference in wear rate scale for the Al 201-Thornel 50 composite.)

9. Wear and friction behavior of various metal matrix-graphite composites and their matrix materials against AISI 4620 steel. (Shaded bars indicate composites. Open bars indicate matrix materials only.)

(a) TIN-THORNEL 50

(b) COPPER-THORNEL 50

(c) Al 6061-FORTAFIL 4R

10. SEM micrographs of worn surfaces of three metal matrix-graphite fiber composites against AISI 4620 steel.